

Use of Active Learning Methods to Develop the Military-Professional Direction of the Course

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Abstract:

This article highlights the importance of using active learning methods for the development of the military-professional direction of the course, the content and specific aspects of individual-oriented educational technologies.

Keywords: educational technologies, military-professional orientation, interactive education, innovative education, educational methods, creative assignments, problem situations.

One of the main directions of the military reforms implemented in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to increase the quality of professional training of officers, which, in turn, will determine the change in the image of the higher military educational institution of Uzbekistan and the training of aviation specialists system [2]. The basis of the correct choice of profession is the professional orientation of a person. Accordingly, the choice of a military profession is based on a military-professional direction, which some military researchers associate primarily with the important professional qualities of officers as civil servants [1]. It is clear that without a sufficiently high level and stability of the military professional orientation, an optimal correlation between the future officer and his chosen profession is impossible. The military-professional direction of a person is not an immutable quality and can change during the stages of its formation (before entering the university) and development (period of professional education), strengthening during professional activity.

Inadequate formation of the military-professional direction of young people entering higher military educational institutions not only reduces the level of successful adaptation in the first months of their studies, but also makes it difficult to develop the important professional qualities of the military, as well as personal content, violation of military discipline, it leads to a decrease in

educational results and, as a result, poor learning of cadets and, as a result, exclusion from studies. According to some data, 7,000 to 8,000 cadets drop out of military educational institutions every year [4]. Therefore, the relevance of the development of the military professional direction in the educational process is determined by the tasks of improving the quality of training of specialists and reducing economic losses as a result of the expulsion of cadets. The content of the overall educational process, the nature of the cadets' educational and professional activities, the forms and methods of teaching and training used, the relationship between teachers and cadets should be aimed at developing the professional direction of future officers, in terms of modern requirements, as well as the needs of a developing person.

Based on the analysis of the problem situation of the cadet's military-professional orientation in pedagogical theory and practice, we came to the conclusion that the development of the military-professional orientation of the cadet's personality can be considered a step-by-step process, thus it is a complex, controlled, continuous, dynamic process, during it, changes occur in the qualitative characteristics of the military-professional direction of the cadet's personality.

In the absence of specially organized measures for the development of the military-professional direction of the cadets, the tendency of self-development of the motivation for military-professional activity in the first three years of the cadets' studies is its decrease at the university level. The analysis of the data obtained during the survey among the first-year students of the Higher Military Aviation Institute of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2023 shows that by the end of the first semester of study, the level of the military-professional direction will decrease occurs in every third cadet. Consequently, the relevance of targeted measures for the development of the military-professional orientation of the cadets of the 1st-3rd year is unquestionable.

The process of developing the military-professional orientation of cadets at the university can be represented by the following stages:

The general aspect of the development of the military-professional direction of the cadets' personality at each of the listed stages is to determine the progress of the process of mastering new forms of professional activity.

The basis for their determination was that the characteristics of the military professional direction change during certain periods of training, and this is related to the nature and content of the cadets'

educational and professional activities and the level of professional development of the person achieved during this period. Practical work on the development of the military-professional direction of the cadets should be formed taking into account the stages of development that we have considered, setting goals, choosing work forms and methods in accordance with it. The success of the development of the military-professional orientation of the cadets depends to a large extent on the activation of the cognitive interests of the cadets and the provision of educational tools for them to have a positive attitude towards mastering the chosen military specialty. Local researchers believe that this method of developing a person's professional direction is activation in educational activities. The university can use various means of activation:

1. well-thought-out system of practical and cognitive tasks;
2. learning algorithmization;
3. problem education;
4. involvement of cadets in research;
5. reasonable means of control and self-control, self-education of cadets;
6. qualitative improvement of the educational process, extensive use of advanced trends in teaching theory and practice;
7. creation of vocationally oriented training courses, vocationally oriented educational and methodological complexes;
8. Special education system etc.

By active teaching methods, we mean methods aimed at increasing the activity of the subject in the learning process, in contrast to traditional approaches, where the student plays a more passive role. Similar content is included in the concept of "intensive training methods" [3]. It is very conditional to describe these methods as active, since passive teaching methods do not exist in principle. Any learning assumes a certain level of activity of the subject, and learning is impossible without it. But this level of activity really varies, and it can be much higher when using active methods. Thus, G. Shchedrovitsky called the active methods of teaching and training that allow students to "learn the necessary knowledge and skills in a short time and with less effort" by consciously "forming the necessary knowledge" calls" [5].

Among the methods of active training that can be successfully used to develop the military-professional orientation of cadets, it is possible to single out educational discussions. Elements of discussion (conflict, clash of positions, deliberate sharpening and even exaggeration of contradictions in the material under discussion) can be used in almost any form of organizational training, including lectures. The division of discussion participants into certain groups activates socio-psychological mechanisms of value-oriented unity formation, collectivist identification, etc., which strengthen or even give rise to new motives for activity. Due to the emotional impulse received during the discussion, it is important to have a strong effect, usually in the form of search or cognitive activity.

The topic of discussion can be meaningful problems related to the important features of the profession. The results of such discussions (especially when specific situations of moral choice are created) change human behavior much more strongly than the simple acquisition of certain professional norms at the level of knowledge. It is known that faith does not appear by itself, suddenly, but is born as a result of the clash of different views and the comparison of opposite opinions. Thus, discussion methods work not only as a teaching tool, but also as an educational tool, which is especially important because the inventory of educational methods is even less. Active training methods that can be used to develop military-professional orientation of cadets include

game methods (exercise, simulation, role-playing, organizational activity, business, etc.). They are not strictly classified, because they often differ for different reasons and mostly overlap.

A. A. Verbitsky defines the business game as a form of recreating the meaningful and social content of the specialist's future professional activity, modeling the system of relations typical of this activity in general [1]. This re-creation is achieved through iconic tools, models and roles played by other people. With the correct organization of the game, the student performs a quasi-professional activity, that is, a professional activity in form, but an educational activity in terms of results and main content.

However, we must not forget that the simulation teaching model always simplifies the real situation and especially often deprives it of elements of dynamism and development. Usually the student deals only with "sections" of the various stages of development of the situation. But this is the inevitable price to pay for the right to make mistakes (the absence of serious consequences that may occur when making wrong decisions in real conditions), the cheapness of models, the ability to reproduce situations in models that are usually impossible. An effective means of developing a person's military-professional direction is to attract cadets to participate in the activities of the military-scientific society. Vocational training aimed at the student can ensure independence and creative approach to the choice of a field of study, the ability to find the most reasonable solutions to labor problems.

It is appropriate to use simulation and game situations in the process of formation of practical skills in training sessions on special subjects. Due to the fact that at this stage of the development of the cadet's military-professional direction, the revision of the system of professional values, the revision and correction of the professional choice are carried out, the identification of the natural essence of this crisis, the search for the individual, and thus its elimination are important tasks. and determining the factors that determine the successful development of the military-professional direction. At this stage, taking into account the influence of students and the growing authority of the teacher, priority should be given to active group methods of psychological and pedagogical support.

It is necessary to help the cadet to identify external and internal obstacles to professionalization and to find opportunities to eliminate them. For this purpose, the psychologists of the professional selection group and the university's department of educational affairs can use the system of activation methods that stimulate the level of formation of a personal professional plan, specially organized classes to clarify the options for professionalization. This work, in our opinion, should not be carried out from time to time, depending on the situation, but should be introduced as a necessary element of the professional training of military personnel. At the same time, work with cadets whose level of military-professional orientation is characterized by a steady decline or has reached a critical value is, as a rule, incorrect due to the low efficiency of the results. This category of cadets requires administrative measures and a decision on the advisability of continuing studies at the university.

Engaging in professional activities that match a person's capabilities ensures his effectiveness. The student's abilities are recognized by others and begin to be recognized by their carriers. Realizing one's abilities under favorable conditions leads to the emergence of an additional motive for activity and the need to further diversify it. The demand for oneself increases, the sense of responsibility to society for the results of one's activity increases. In this way, training allows the cadet to successfully begin to apply effectively in practice, for example, to best demonstrate the knowledge, skills and qualities acquired during military training; Implementation of control and reorganization of activities in the interests of strengthening the combat readiness and capability of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Thus, the step-by-step development of the level of the military-professional orientation of the cadets of the military educational institution, the selection of practical work forms, methods and tools ensures the achievement of the necessary level of the military-professional orientation, as well as the tasks of service and educational activities that are personally important is expressed in the conversion to goals; building professional confidence; stability of interest in the military profession; persistence in achieving positive results in education and professional activity; high results of professional and educational activities and satisfaction with the choice of an officer's profession.

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